

The Effect of E-Learning in Teaching Vocational Education on Academic Achievement among Seventh-Grade Students in Jordan

Fares George Tannous

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 17, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: December 18, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : E-Learning, Vocational Education, Academic Achievement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10675703</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to examine the effect of e-learning in teaching Professional Education on academic achievement among 7-grade primary education students in Jordan. The study sample comprised 48 students from two primary education schools in Madaba. The students were divided into two groups: The control group was taught using a traditional teaching method, whereas the experimental group was taught the same unit using a direct e-learning method. An achievement test on the subject unit was developed. Its validity and reliability were verified. The equivalency of the two groups was established by comparing average scores in the first semester. Pretest and posttest scores revealed that the experimental group, which employed e-learning, significantly outperformed the control group, which used traditional methods. Pretest scores were similar for both groups, but posttest scores diverged significantly, with the experimental group achieving a mean score of 15.18 compared to the control group's 10.25. Statistical analysis (ANOVA) confirmed the differences were significant ($F=29.145$, $p<0.05$), indicating that e-learning significantly enhances academic achievement.</i></p>

Introduction

The emergence of new theories of teaching has made learning to shift from being teacher-oriented to being student-oriented. Moreover, the development of new communication devices has enabled modern teachers to use modern methods of teaching and learning, get free from time and space barriers, and keep on learning at any time and place according to their needs and demands (Hosseini et al., 2015).

E-learning is one of the most important ways and learning environments in the information era that support the educational process and transform education into the stage of creativity and development of skills and interaction from the process of indoctrination. Therefore, efforts and experiences related to this type of learning are given due attention worldwide. (Zare, Sarikhani, Salari, & Mansouri, 2016). Moreover, E-learning challenges the traditional method and provides new solutions for problems. For instance, the role of teachers is probably changing from importers of knowledge to expeditors of knowledge (Haverila & Barkhi, 2009).

There are many definitions for e-learning from the Educational dictionary: (Levy, 2006) defined E-learning as a system based on technology, organization

, and management that bestows the students to learn via the internet and facilitates their learning. Wanting et al. (2000) define e-learning as acquiring disseminated knowledge using electronic devices.

Also, E-learning can be understood as an educational process, using information and communication technologies to create training, to distribute learning content, communication between students and teachers and for management of studies" (Wagner, 2005)

Bowles (2000) show that E-learning uses telecommunications technology to get information to achieve the teaching and learning objectives. It can be said that e-learning refers to the use of systems of electronic education such as computers, the internet, multimedia disks, electronic magazines, virtual newscasts, etc., whose purposes are to reduce time and expenses and achieve better, faster, and easier learning (Zare et al., 2016).

Moreover, E-learning contains different educational tools in learning and educating. E-learning has the same meaning with "technology-enhanced learning (TEL), computer-based instruction (CBI), computer-based training (CBT), computer-assisted instruction or computer-aided instruction (CAI), internet-based training (IBT), web-based training (WBT), online education, virtual education, virtual learning environments (VLE) (which are also called learning platforms), m-learning, and digital educational collaboration" (E-learning, 2013).

A review of studies conducted on e-learning applications and their impact on learning suggests that using this teaching method in the teaching-learning process can lead to training effectiveness. The study of Christmann & Lemaitres' (2006) demonstrates that this new teaching does not decrease the time of teaching but encourages more active learning and a better understanding of technology for students to proceed with their abilities. Payne et al. (2009) study displayed that workplace learner can be better assisted by the e-learning method rather than the traditional method as they let asynchronous learning and private study, which are valued

by staff who have other requests on their time and are more relaxed getting tuition privately. Paechter & Maier (2010) studied Austrian students' favorite aspects of eLearning courses. Their study showed that Students chose online learning because it provides a prominent learning material structure. They chose face-to-face learning for communication goals in which shared comprehension has to be extracted. Zarie, Zavaraki & Rezaei (2011) found that using an e-portfolio significantly improved students' attitudes, motivation, and academic achievement. Bhuasiri, Xaymoungkhoun, Zo, Rho, & Ciganek (2012) believe that the essentials for implementing effective e-learning in developing countries are technology awareness, motivation, and changing learners' behavior. Keshavarz et al. (2013) found that e-learning positively impacts students' academic achievements. Mahmoodi et al. (2015) found that using e-learning in the physiology teaching-learning process improves students learning and creativity. Zare et al. (2015) also found that the learning and recollection of students who were educated in multimedia methods are more than the learning and recollection of students who were educated in traditional methods.

The Study Problem

The purpose of this study is to investigate whether or not e-learning methodologies have a substantial effect on the academic achievement of seventh-grade students in Jordan who are enrolled in Professional Education. More specifically, the study will compare traditional teaching methods to direct e-learning approaches. The objective of this study is to ascertain whether these differences are statistically significant at the level of 0.05 or less. This will be accomplished by utilizing the results of the pre-test and post-test to evaluate the influence on two groups of pupils who attend two primary schools in Madaba. Understanding the efficacy of e-learning and guiding future educational techniques in a digital learning landscape that is rapidly evolving are both essential goals that can be accomplished through this investigation.

The Study Question

The study problem can be identified by answering the following central question:

1. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level of (≤ 0.05) between means of achievement scores among seventh-grade students in Professional Education attributed to the teaching method variable?

Previous Studies

Ayanwoye (2023) This research looked at how well children in Nigeria fared after participating in government-sponsored teacher cluster meeting workshops. Schools that took part in the workshop and consented to be part of the study were used to test hypotheses derived from the idea of continuous improvement. The study's design was a quasi-experimental ex-post facto type with a pretest-posttest, control group, and methodology. The tools utilized for this study were the students' pre- and post-workshop achievement scores. To test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance, the data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the research demonstrated noteworthy distinctions in the pre-test and posttest scores of experimental and control groups ($t(1,1476) = -161.79$) and $t(1,1417) = -12.79$, respectively. The posttest scores of the treatment and control groups were $t(1,2884) = 156.62$, while the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group were $t(1,2884) = -12.79$, and the control group scored -158.96 . We spoke about how to make changes to the classroom that would help students do better academically, and we suggested instituting regular professional development opportunities for educators.

Hasan & Murshid (2023) conducted a study aimed to assess how the COVID-19 pandemic affected the curriculum of private schools in Amman, Jordan, both during and after the outbreak. The research topics and hypotheses were to be addressed by use of a ten-paragraph questionnaire. Twenty private schools in Jordan's capital city of Amman were chosen at random from a pool of potential participants in the study. Although there was no discernible effect of gender on e-learning efficiency during the corona pandemic, a positive correlation was found between teachers' years of experience and e-learning efficacy. Overall, the results showed that e-learning efficacy was medium to poor. Several obstacles, including those of a technical, social, economic, and infrastructure nature, contributed to the poor performance of online education during the Corona Pandemic. According to the study, online education could supplement more conventional classroom instruction; it would be especially useful for literature classes; and workshops could be organized to help teachers, students, and parents become more prepared to use online learning.

Alnemrat et al. (2023) This study aims to gain a better understanding of the current state of online learning and to examine, from the viewpoint of faculty members at a prominent Jordanian university, the obstacles that have prevented the successful deployment of online learning. Results from an analysis of 157 faculty members' emailed surveys indicated that, on a 4-point Likert scale, faculty members had a good understanding of e-learning ($M = 3.049$). On a 5-point Likert scale, faculty members frequently used e-learning ($M = 3.640$). Faculty members at Yarmouk University say they get help from their departments when it comes to implementing e-learning, but overall, people aren't sure how to feel about the policy and support hurdles ($M =$

3.567). Regarding the physical and resource limitations, a total of 3,482 academic members at Yarmouk University were unsure of how to respond. The attitude item responses demonstrated that the faculty members of Yarmouk University are open to incorporating e-learning into their lessons ($M = 3.913$). Faculty members were also rather satisfied with the e-learning development plans and techniques, according to the responses ($M = 3.668$). They proved that they had no problems with planning and development and that their methods and plans paid off. When it came to e-learning knowledge, utilization, and obstacles, the data revealed no gender disparities.

Ahmad Albado et al. (2023) study seeks to shed insight on the difficulties encountered by vocational education students in Jordan during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the central area of Jordan, a sample of 1200 freshly joined students was taken from the Vocational Training Corporation. Two parts of the questionnaire were created: one for students and one for infrastructural issues. We made sure the survey was valid and consistent. The results show that there is no statistically significant effect of gender on the amount of difficulties that students face, and that these difficulties are considerable on both the student and infrastructure levels. There is no way that distant learning can meet the demands of practical training without specialized resources. In order to raise the bar for vocational education and training, the study suggests upgrading the facility. In order for the school to successfully execute vocational training programs, more funding is required. Finally, educational policies need to be reviewed thoroughly.

Yachou et al. (2022) The authors of this article zeroed particularly on how COVID-19 has prompted Jordanian universities to adopt digital platforms. Unscheduled school closures in more than 100 countries and the exclusion of over 1 billion students have resulted from efforts to limit the COVID-19 outbreak, which has had a widespread impact on education systems worldwide. This study builds a thorough online learning model and is the first of its kind to investigate how COVID-19 affected the education system within the setting of Jordan's university sector. It helps students at Jordanian institutions summarise their own views and requirements by identifying the elements that impact e-learning adoption and drawing attention to the important relationships; this, in turn, leads to practice. University stakeholders, legislators, professionals, and specialists in Jordan can benefit practically from the study's recommendations. Stakeholders in Jordanian higher education can utilize the results to better understand the variables, make informed decisions, and increase the prevalence of online courses. On top of that, they lend a hand to administrators in creating user-friendly websites and coming up with sound plans to increase e-learning adoption in educational institutions. Two hundred people, including educators, parents, and officials, filled out the questionnaires to provide the data. The study analyzed the collected data using STATA/Regression. The findings showed that COVID-19 has a detrimental impact on education due to disruptions in learning, reduced access to educational and research institutions, employment losses, and an increase in student debt. The results also demonstrated that, because to the epidemic, online learning had to rely heavily on technology from both students and teachers. Thus, online education has long been obstructed by a number of variables, such as inadequate infrastructures that cause problems with power, networks, accessibility, and availability of service, as well as users' lack of digital skills. The research emphasizes the negative consequences of COVID-19 on the educational sphere, the need for schools to accept new technologies, the need of teachers and students improving their digital literacy, and, most significantly, the present worldwide trends and realities in the education sector.

Hazaimah&Ajlouni (2022) The purpose of this research was to gain a better understanding of the challenges that Jordanian vocational education teachers have when using online courses for entry-level students. The study used a descriptive-analytical technique to attain its objectives. The research included 85 educators, both male and female, from the education schools in Kasbat Irbid during the 2021–2022 school year. The researchers produced a questionnaire with twenty-four items, organized into three major categories. From the perspective of Jordanian professional education instructors, the overall mean of the challenges they encountered while implementing online courses for elementary school students was (3.59), indicating a medium level of difficulty. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that the means regarding the challenges experienced by professional education teachers in utilizing e-learning as a result of gender and experience did not differ statistically ($\alpha = 0.05$). The study's findings support the need for ongoing professional development for vocational education educators through the use of online learning and, more specifically, electronic assessment tools and procedures.

Abu-Al-Aish (2021) The purpose of this research was to examine the difficulties encountered by Jordanian institutions when utilizing online learning platforms, as well as the managerial and technological factors that affected the smooth rollout and utilization of such platforms during COVID-19. In order to accomplish the study's goals, the researcher created a questionnaire and sent it out to university professors in Jordan via the internet.

Alameri et al. (2020) In this research, the researchers take a look at how students see online education. The University of Jordan uses digital learning tools such as Moodle, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom. Additionally, it assesses the extent to which students' familiarity with the platforms of Moodle, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom aids in their independent study and academic achievement. The pupils gained valuable experience with online

learning during the three-month COVID-19 pandemic quarantine. A total of 450 students participated in the survey, which consisted of closed-ended questions. A multiple regression model was used to analyze the responses. The model centered on students' predictions regarding their gender, age, level of computer literacy, views on new technologies, learning styles, and the university's usage of e-learning. The benefits and cons of online education as it pertains to high-quality content analysis were detailed. The study's main conclusion was that, when evaluating student perspective, the strategic design of the university's e-learning program—which utilized platforms including Moodle, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom—was more important than individual context variables. In terms of efficiency, students rate the campus's e-learning connectivity as excellent. Students in the domains of new technologies and those with prior experience with computers had a very positive outlook on e-learning.

Using e-platforms during the COVID-19 pandemic had a major impact on their ability to study on their own and their grades.

Conclusion Of The Studies

Taken as a whole, the studies show how the COVID-19 pandemic has altered educational settings and how e-learning has changed this landscape. They show that after teacher development programs in Nigeria, students' academic performance improved significantly, that despite policy, support, and resource barriers, university faculty in Jordan are committed to integrating e-learning, and that online learning in private schools in Jordan is medium to poor effective. Furthermore, there is no statistically significant correlation between gender and the obstacles experienced by Jordan's vocational education system as it attempts to transition to online learning. This article takes a look at how Jordanian universities have gone digital, highlighting the significance of infrastructure in facilitating successful e-learning and the necessity for higher levels of digital literacy among faculty and students.

Methods And Procedure

The study used a quasi-experimental design with a pretest and Posttest with a control group.

Study Population and Sample

The study population consisted of all seventh-grade students in private schools in Madaba, Jordan, in the first term of the academic year of 2018-2019. The researcher chose a purposive sample of 48 female and male students in the seventh grade (24 experimental, 24 control). The experimental group that was taught according to e-learning included 24 students (11 males, 13 females), and the control group included 24 students (12 males, 12 females) who were taught according to the traditional teaching method. First and before entering the educational intervention, both groups took the pretest.

Equalization of study groups

To check the equalization of the study groups (control, experimental), a t-test was applied to students' scores in the two groups in the achievement pretest. The result is shown in Table (1).

Table 1. t-test on scores of achievement pretest of experimental and control groups

Instrument	Group	Num.	Mean	S.D.	t-test	Sig.
Achievement test	Experimental	24	8.63	2.85	0.143	0.880
	Control	24	8.71	2.91		

Table (1) indicates that the value of the t-test was (.143), which is not statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). The result reveals that there is no statistical significance between the average scores of students of experimental and control groups in the achievement pretest. That is, the experimental and control groups are Equivalent.

Instrument

The instrument used for data collection was an achievement test developed by the researcher. The researcher-made achievement test contains 20 objective items. It has high reliability of .84. It has face validity, as confirmed by teachers.

Instrument validity

To check the validity of the research instrument, the researcher presented the achievement test to a panel of 10 experts experiencing and specializing in measurement and evaluation, curricula and teaching methods, and supervisors of Professional Education. The notes and comments of the experts were considered, and the test was modified based on them. Thus, the achievement test consisted of 20 items.

Instrument Reliability

After applying the achievement test to the exploratory sample consisting of 22 students, the Internal Consistency Reliability was calculated by Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient which was (0.84), and this value is accepted for this study.

Study variables

The independent variables in this study are 1- (e-learning, traditional),

The dependent variable of the study is academic achievement.

Statistical Treatments

The researcher used the following statistical analyses: Means and standard deviations to calculate academic achievement according to the group variable and gender variable,

ANCOVA to check the effect of group on academic achievement,

f- test to check the equalization of the study groups and to calculate the significance of the difference in academic achievement according to gender variable.

The Study Results

The first question is: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level of (≤ 0.05) between means of academic achievement scores among seventh-grade students attributed to the teaching method variable?

To answer this question, means, standard deviations, and modified means of academic achievement scores are calculated according to the group variable (experimental, control), as shown in table (2).

Table 2. Means, standard deviations, of academic achievement scores according to the group variable

Group	No	pretest		posttest	
		Mean	S. D	Mean	S. D
control	24	8.71	2.91	10.25	2.97
Experimental	24	8.63	2.85	15.18	2.48

Table (2) demonstrates that the mean of the pretest for the control group students is (8.71) and the standard deviation is (2.91). In addition, the mean of the pretest for the experimental group students is (8.63), and the standard deviation is (2.85). Further, the mean of the Posttest in the control group of students is (10.25) and the standard deviation is (2.97). Furthermore, the mean of the Posttest for the experimental group students is (15.18), and the standard deviation is (2.48).

Table (2) also reveals apparent differences in mean academic achievement scores attributed to the group variable (experimental, control). To show the statistically significant difference between means, an ANOVA test was used, as shown in table (3).

Table 3. ANCOVA test for the effect of group variable on academic achievement

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean squares	F	Sig
Pretest (accompanied)	216.527	1	216.527	69.155	0.000
Group	90.879	1	90.879	29.145	0.000
Error	159.423	45	3.168		
Total	6648.152	48			

Table (3) shows that the value of F is (29.145), which means that there are statistically significant differences at the significance level of (≤ 0.05) between means of academic achievement scores among seventh-grade students in Professional Education attributed to the teaching method variable. In addition, table (4) demonstrates statistically significant differences attributable to the experimental group. This result indicates that teaching by using e-learning increases academic achievement scores contrary to the traditional method. Thus, such differences appeared for the experimental group on the academic achievement test.

Discussion Of The Results

Findings from the first study that showed how e-learning improved students' grades are in line with those from Ayanwoye's (2023) study of Nigerian teacher training programs. Hasan and Murshid (2023) found that private schools in Jordan struggle with e-learning efficacy. Their findings point to a complicated landscape where factors like digital literacy and infrastructure are just as important as teaching approaches.

Results from studies on faculty attitudes and difficulties in vocational education (Ahmad Albado et al., 2023) and online education (Alnemrat et al., 2023) highlight the complex nature of the obstacles to online education, which include problems with policy and support. The investigations have shown that there are broader obstacles that need to be addressed if e-learning is to be effectively implemented, and these challenges are similar to those previously mentioned.

The findings of Yachou et al. (2022) about the adoption of digital platforms at Jordanian universities during COVID-19, in conjunction with the widespread agreement regarding the necessity of strengthening digital literacy and infrastructure, are a reflection of the implications that the initial study had for the enhancement of teaching techniques through the use of technology. The findings of these research together advocate for a balanced approach to e-learning, which acknowledges the benefits of e-learning in terms of improved academic achievements while also admitting the vital need for supportive measures to overcome the inherent hurdles that e-learning presents along the way.

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Author Information

Fares George Tannous
Master in MBA/E-Government
The Ministry of Education, Jordan
